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Parents' Perception and Plights on Electronic Payment Systems in Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigated parents' perception and plights on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State. Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. Population of the study was all parents in the 447 private secondary schools in Delta State, while 224 parents (77 males and 147 females) were sampled for the study using convenience sampling technique. Instrument used for data collection was a 15 item questionnaire titled "Parents Perspective on Electronic Payment Systems Questionnaire" (PPEPSQ) which was face and content validated by two experts in Educational Management, University of Port Harcourt. Reliability of the questionnaire was estimated using Cronbach alpha and gave a reliability index of 0.91 which shows that the questionnaire was reliable. The 224 copies of questionnaire administered were all retrieved on the spot by the researcher and four Research Assistants. Research questions raised were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that the parents had positive perception about the use of electronic payment systems despite challenges such as high cost of using the platforms. It was revealed that the introduction of multiple payment channels will help mitigate their plights. It was recommended that the private schools should adequately sensitize their parents on the use of these platforms for effective school administration.

Keywords: Parents, Electronic, Payment, Perception, School

INTRODUCTION

The advancement in technology has brought about visible changes on how businesses are conducted all over the world and this includes changes in the process of educational administration especially in private secondary schools. There is no doubt that public secondary schools make deliberate effort in digitalizing all administrative processes for organizational efficiency and effectiveness and this includes how financial transactions are being handled. Alluding to this fact, Teoh et al., (2013) stated that advancement in the internet has greatly changed and facilitated development in online modes of payment which has gained popularity all over including private schools.

Today, in order to facilitate proper financial management, private secondary schools are adopting different electronic means of financial transactions for effective service delivery, and this comes with a lot of benefits and challenges for their trading partners especially parents. Eelu and Nakakawa (2018) stated that various electronic payment methods have so far being developed and this includes credit card payment methods, digital cash system, electronic cheque system, smart cards based electronic payment system and mobile payments, and there is no private school where one or more of this payment methods is not in use. However, whether or not parents are satisfied and skilled in the use of the channels available in the schools they patronize remains unclear.

All organizations believe in the use of electronic payment methods especially the private ones because they believe it comes with lot of advantages, but this does not mean that there are no bottlenecks with their usage especially among parents who are end users. In fact, there is a general notion that it takes time for innovation to be accepted and this establishes the fact that some parents may hold certain reservation about the electronic payment systems used in the schools they patronize but when there are not complain mechanisms, they have no option but to flow with the *statusquo*. In fact, Martinez et al., (2015) noted in their study that till date there are differences in the experiences of internet users, and this is largely due to lack of knowledge which makes it difficult for users to actually maximize the benefits for which such facility was instituted.

On the other hand, scholars such as Singh et al., (2014) identified lack of usability, lack of security, lack of eligibility, high usage costs for customers and merchants, lack of efficiency and lack of consistency as some of the challenges that some of the users of these platforms face. Similarly, Teoh et al. (2013) noted that there had been cases of financial loses, physical, social and performance risks that some users of electronic innovations such as electronic platforms face which has far reaching implications. The use of electronic payment systems is sometimes viewed by users with a sense of apprehension especially in developing economies such as ours as a result of lack of adequacy and uniformity which makes it difficult for some users to make definite opinions about their use. Additionally, scholars such as Barkhordari (2017), Okifo and Igbunu (2015) as well as Nguyen and Huynh (2018) outlined that electronic payment systems suffer several setbacks and opposition as a result of lack of physical receipts, lack of awareness, low customer trust level, security issues, high transaction costs set by mobile network operators, Inadequate government policies or legal protections, social and economic factors like low income and literacy rates, and inadequate infrastructure. These factors remain a huge challenge to the financial inclusivity of private secondary schools when it comes to electronic payment methods.

Several studies have been conducted by researchers to investigate the perception of different stakeholders on the use of electronic payment methods in schools. Mwalongo (2018) investigated a study on parents' perception on integration of information communication technology (ICT) in education and its influence in school choice in private pre-primary schools in Tanzania. Five parents whose children attend private pre-primary schools in urban Njombe provided the study's data. According to the study, the majority of parents in Njombe who enroll their kids in private pre-primary schools think that information and communications technology (ICT) will have a significant impact on their kids' futures. Additionally, the study found that parents often choose private pre-primary schools based on the availability of ICT facilities. The research found that, in addition to parents having a favorable opinion of ICT, most schools lack the necessary resources for teaching and learning ICT, and parents are concerned about how to properly supervise their children's use of ICT.

Espeleta (2022) investigated utilization of standard electronic payment system among private higher education institutions in the Province of Albay. The study used a mixed method of qualitative and quantitative research design. The Gcash app is one of the most popular ones used when making online payments, per the data shown. It is easier to use and more readily available. Additionally, the perception of the chosen private HEIs has demonstrated a strong correlation to one another when using the Kendall Coefficient of Concordance, leading to a rare use based on the data analysis. The private institutions that were chosen currently accept electronic payments. Schools are still implementing electronic payment

systems, but they have not yet considered how to give students and parents the most control over those payments.

Ritthitrapitop and Hamra (2019) conducted another study on organization and parental perceptions of electronic payments by selected Seventh-day Adventist (SDA) International Schools in Thailand. An approach to descriptive research design was used. The data was gathered using interviews and questionnaires. The hypotheses were put to test with multiple regression. Eight employees from the school's finance department and the 319 parents who had previously paid the schools electronically were chosen as respondents. Data analysis methods included frequency distributions, percentages, means, standard deviations, and multiple regression (stepwise multiple regression analysis). The findings showed that the "High" rating was given to the factors of benefits, trust, self-efficacy, ease of use, and security. Benefits received the highest mean score (4.16), followed by self-efficacy (3.91), usability (3.89), trust (3.81), and security (3.55), in that order. Additionally, all variables were significantly related to parental perceptions of e-payments at the 0.05 level of significance, with the exception of self-efficacy. Findings from focus groups with the finance staff at each school showed that their opinions of electronic transactions for receiving and disbursing money were influenced by factors like usability, trust, security, and benefits.

On the other hand, Sallaoum *et al.*, (2019) conducted an analysis of innovative study of E-payment systems adoption in higher education in the UAE. There were 289 students from 6 different universities in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) who participated in the study. For analysis, structural equation modeling with partial least squares was used. The empirical findings indicated a significant negative relationship between perceived security/privacy and perceived risk and a significant positive relationship between perceived benefit and performance expectancy and the students' intention to use e-payment systems. However, the findings revealed that trust has little bearing on students' intention to use e-payment systems. The findings of this study offer new, current information on the adoption of e-payment systems in higher educational institutions.

Oyelami *et al.*, (2020) carried out another study on electronic payment adoption and customers spending growth in Nigeria. The study used both primary and secondary data sources from bank customers in Lagos State who make use of electronic payment methods. A questionnaire was given to 420 customers in order to collect data. Frequency, percentage, and Pearson correlation were used to analyze the data. According to the study's findings, adoption of electronic payments in Nigeria is positively correlated with factors such as convenience, security, safety, trust, and social influence. It was also demonstrated that access to the internet, point of sale devices, income level, financial inclusion, and education level were other crucial determinants. These various studies demonstrate that users must be more resolute in their actions if electronic payment methods are to be adopted in schools.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the parents' perception and plights on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. find out parents' perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State
2. identify the plights of parents using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State
3. ascertain the strategies for mitigating the challenges of parents in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are parents' perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State?
2. What are the plights of parents using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State?

3. What are the strategies for mitigating the challenges of parents in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their plights using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State
3. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on the strategies for mitigating their challenges in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of all parents in the 447 private secondary schools in Delta State. The sample for the study was 224 parents (77 males and 147 females) as 2 parents were sampled from 25% of the private schools in the State using convenience sampling technique. The instrument used for gathering data was a 15 item questionnaire titled “Parents Perspective on Electronic Payment Systems Questionnaire” (PPEPSQ). The questionnaire had two sections namely; Section A for collection of demographic data on the respondents and Second B which contained the 15 questionnaire items which were responded to on a four point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with weighted scores of 4,3, 2 and 1. These weights were summed and divided by 4 to arrive at 2.50 which was the criterion mean score used for agreeing or disagreeing with the questionnaire items. The questionnaire was face and content validated by two experts in Educational Management, University of Port Harcourt. The reliability of the questionnaire was estimated using Cronbach alpha and gave a reliability index of 0.91 which shows that the questionnaire was reliable. The 224 copies of questionnaire administered were all retrieved on the spot by the researcher and four Research Assistants. Research questions raised were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question One: *What are parents’ perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores on parents’ perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

S/No	Items	Male Parents n=77		Female Parents n=147		Mean Set X \bar{X}	Decision
		Mean \bar{X}_1	SD	Mean \bar{X}_2	SD		
1	Making payment electronically makes transactions very fast	2.72	0.80	2.84	0.73	2.78	Agreed
2	Electronic payment guarantees transparency in payment procedures	2.66	0.82	2.89	0.71	2.78	Agreed
3	Uneducated users can be easily marginalized	2.44	0.97	2.30	0.96	2.37	Disagreed
4	There are a lot of risks associated with electronic payment methods	2.69	0.81	2.90	0.71	2.80	Agreed
5	Generating transaction evidence is difficult electronically	2.42	0.98	2.40	0.94	2.41	Disagreed
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		2.59	0.88	2.67	0.81	2.63	Agreed

Table 1 showed that the responses of male parents were agreed for items 1-4 with mean values that were greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50 while item 5 with mean score of 2.42 which is lesser than the criterion mean score was disagreed indicating that they disagreed that generating transaction evidence was difficult. On the part of the female parents, items 1, 2 and 4 had mean values that were greater than the criterion mean score while items 3 and 5 were lesser implying that the respondents disagreed with those items. However, the grand mean values of 2.59 and 2.67 from both parents align with the average mean set score of 2.63 to indicate that they averagely agreed with the items listed as parents' perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Question Two: *What are the plights of parents using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores on the plights of parents using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

S/No	Items	Male Parents n=77		Female Parents n=147		Mean Set X \bar{X}	Decision
		Mean \bar{X}_1	SD	Mean \bar{X}_2	SD		
6	High cost of transaction charges makes electronic payment method unpalatable	2.77	0.78	2.96	0.69	2.87	Agreed
7	The security of financial transactions is not often guaranteed	2.41	0.98	2.44	0.93	2.43	Disagreed
8	Resolving financial discrepancies can be frustrating	2.79	0.77	2.98	0.68	2.89	Agreed
9	Electronic payment methods is not very effective	2.38	0.99	2.46	0.92	2.42	Disagreed
10	Using electronic payment methods can be mentally demanding	2.39	0.99	2.53	0.91	2.46	Disagreed
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		2.55	0.90	2.67	0.83	2.61	Agreed

Table 2 indicated that the male parents responded to items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 with mean scores of 2.77, 2.41, 2.79, 2.39 and 2.39 while the female parents responded to the same set of items with mean scores of 2.96, 2.44, 2.98, 2.46 and 2.53. Items with mean values above the criterion mean scores were agreed while the others were disagreed. The greatest mean set score of 2.89 from items 8 showed that resolving financial discrepancies was the major electronic payment challenge that parents faced. The grand mean scores of 2.55 and 2.67 from the male and female parents is in tandem with the average mean set score of 2.61 which indicated that the respondents averagely agreed with the items listed as the plights of parents using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Question Three: What are the strategies for mitigating the challenges of parents in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation scores on the strategies for mitigating the challenges of parents in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

S/No	Items	Male Parents n=77		Female Parents n=147		Mean Set		Decision
		Mean \bar{X}_1	SD	Mean \bar{X}_2	SD	X \bar{X}		
11	There is need for introduction of multiple payment channels	2.80	0.76	2.98	0.68	2.89		Agreed
12	Schools should institutionalize financial resolution units	2.82	0.75	2.57	0.89	2.70		Agreed
13	Incentives should be provided to those who make use of online payment methods	2.79	0.76	2.96	0.69	2.88		Agreed
14	Adequate sensitization should be provided on how the payment platforms work	2.88	0.73	2.96	0.69	2.92		Agreed
15	Adequate time should be given to parents who wish to engage electronic payment methods	2.70	0.80	2.60	0.87	2.65		Agreed
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		2.80	0.76	2.81	0.76	2.81		Agreed

Table 3 established that the responses of the male parents of 2.80, 2.82, 2.79, 2.88 and 2.70 on items 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 as well as that of the female parents of 2.98, 2.57, 2.96, 2.96 and 2.60 were all above the criterion mean score of 2.50 used for decision making and as such were all agreed. The grand mean score of 2.80 from the male parents and 2.81 from the female parents as well as the average mean set score of 2.81 established that the parents averagely agreed with the items listed as the strategies for mitigating the challenges of parents in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

Table 4: Summary of z-test analysis on the difference in the mean ratings of male and female parents on their perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Parents	77	2.59	0.88	222	0.66	1.96	0.05	Not Rejected
Female Parents	147	2.67	0.81					

Table 4 indicated that the value of z-cal. was determined to be 1.96 at 222 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. The value of z-cal. on the other hand was estimated to be 0.66. Since the table value of z-crit. of 1.96 was more than the estimated value of z-cal. of 0.66, the null hypothesis was not rejected

indicating that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their plights using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate

Table 5: Summary of z-test analysis on the difference in the mean ratings of male and female parents on their plights using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Parents	77	2.55	0.90	222	0.97	1.96	0.05	Not Rejected
Female Parents	147	2.67	0.83					

Table 5 indicated that the value of z-cal. was determined to be 1.96 at 222 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. The value of z-cal. on the other hand was estimated to be 0.97. Since the table value of z-crit. of 1.96 was more than the estimated value of z-cal. of 0.97, the null hypothesis was not rejected indicating that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their plights using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on the strategies for mitigating their challenges in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate

Table 6: Summary of z-test analysis on the difference in the mean ratings of male and female parents on the strategies for mitigating their challenges in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Parents	77	2.80	0.76	222	0.09	1.96	0.05	Not Rejected
Female Parents	147	2.81	0.76					

Table 6 indicated that the value of z-cal. was determined to be 1.96 at 222 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. The value of z-cal. on the other hand was estimated to be 0.09. Since the table value of z-crit. of 1.96 was more than the estimated value of z-cal. of 0.09, the null hypothesis was not rejected indicating that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on the strategies for mitigating their challenges in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the showed that the parents sampled for the study agreed on the items as parents' perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate. It was also shown that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their perception on electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta Sate. This finding align with the outcome of the study by Espeleta (2022) which indicated that parents have positive perception about the use of electronic payment methods even though they are not in full control of the process. In the study, the parents agreed that electronic payment makes transactions fast and transparent. This agreed with the result of the study by Oyelami et al., (2020) which showed that respondents believe electronic payment methods are convenient. They also agreed that there are risks associated with using electronic platforms for payment in the school. However, both the male and female parents disagreed that electronic payment systems will make some uneducated parents to be marginalized. This may be because several other

electronic methods of payment are used in schools such as the use of Point of Sale (POS) machines which can be used by anyone. They also disagreed that generating transaction evidence is challenging. However, this may not be applicable to all electronic payment methods especially where platforms that issue receipts are not used.

It was indicated in the findings of the study that the respondents averagely agreed with the items listed as the plights of parents using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State, and that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on their plights using electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State. In the study, the parents indicated that some of the plights they encounter in the use of electronic payment platforms is that it comes with high cost. This is true especially where bank charges are made for each transaction initiated by parents for their children. This is often avoided when cash payments are made. The parents also indicated from their responses that another challenge they face is that resolving financial discrepancies is usually difficult. This is in relation to the finding of the study by Sallaoum *et al.*, (2019) which indicated that the issue of trust is why some users shy away from electronic payment methods. This often happens when transactions are not successfully completed which leaves both parties in the dark and some of these issues take a while to be resolved. However, the parents disagreed that there is no security with using electronic payment methods or that electronic payment methods are not effective. This aligns with the outcome of the study by Ritthitrapitop and Hamra (2019) which establishes that electronic payment methods come with security which users appreciate. This suggests that the parents have some level of confidence with this payment method. However, while the male parents disagreed, the female parents agreed that electronic payment method can be mentally demanding. This suggests that the female parents may struggle with using this platform compared to their male counterpart. This may however be due to the several procedures that may need to be followed when some of these electronic payment platforms are being used.

The findings of the study showed that the parents agreed on the items as the strategies for mitigating the challenges of parents in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State. It was also shown that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female parents on the strategies for mitigating their challenges in the use of electronic payment systems in private secondary schools in Delta State. The parents in their response suggested the need for schools to introduce multiple electronic payment platforms and this is important to give parents payment platform options which will meet their peculiarities. The parents also agreed that schools should have a financial resolution unit. Although this should be part of the functions of the account department but the schools may need to strengthen this aspect of their service delivery. The respondents also indicated that it will be good to give incentives to those who use electronic payment methods and this no doubt will help to digitalize payment methods in the schools. The parents also indicated the need for adequate sensitization and time for those who wish to use the electronic payment methods provided by these schools and this no doubt will improve the process of school administration in the study area. According to Mwalongo (2018), parents have worries about the use of ICT and it is only through adequate sensitization and guidance that these fears and inabilities can be dealt with for effective school administration.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded based on the findings of the study that despite the fact that parents see electronic payment system in the schools as a positive development, majority of them still have challenging reservations about the system irrespective of their gender and this needs to be resolved for the gains of electronic payment system to be maximized in the private schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Private schools should institutionalize a complaint mechanism that will enable parents register the challenges they face in the process of carrying out their electronic transactions and to also receive help for smooth electronic transactions with the school.

2. Private secondary schools should put in place different electronic payment options that will enable parents use any of the platforms that meets their need and convenience.
3. Adequate sensitization and stakeholder meeting should be held between parents and the school through the Parents Teachers Association (PTA) platform to reach an agreement and also acquire relevant information on the best electronic payment option that will meet the need of both parties.

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